

SUPERSATURATION COEFFICIENT AND THE PARTICLE SIZE OF THE SOLUTE

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In a previous note (*this journal*, 1945, 22, 45), it has been shown that the supersaturation coefficient is inversely proportional to the size of the particles with which that solution is in equilibrium. Thus, for all values of τ , which make K/τ less than unity we have,

$$\frac{S - S_n}{S_n} = K/\tau \quad \dots (1)$$

The value of K being constant is given by $2M\sigma/RTd$ (where the terms have the same significance as mentioned before).

A concrete example shows that the value of K is such that it verges on the dimensions of a colloidal particle. In the case of gypsum ($d=2.32$, $\sigma=1050$ ergs per unit area at 25° , $M = 136$; Hulett, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1901, 37, 385) $\tau = 4.93 \times 10^{-4}$ cm. or about $50\mu\mu$. When, however, τ grows smaller and verges on the threshold of "colloidal solutions", the linear relationship of equation (1) no longer holds and one may calculate only the approximate supersaturation coefficient in the different regions.

Particle size.	Approx. supersat. coeff.
50 $\mu\mu$ to 25 $\mu\mu$	1.7 to 6.4
25 $\mu\mu$ to 10 $\mu\mu$	6.4 to 147
10 $\mu\mu$ to 5 $\mu\mu$	22025

When τ grows still smaller one leaves the field of colloids and enters practically that of molecules.

It would be interesting to recall here that Von Weimarn ("Grundzuge der Dispersoid Chemie", 1911) in an investigation of the conditions of precipitation of slightly soluble substances arrived at the equation

$$\delta = \frac{c}{s} \cdot \eta \quad \dots (2)$$

where c is the potential solubility of the sparingly soluble substance, s , its normal solubility and η , the viscosity of the medium and δ , the degree of dispersion of the precipitate formed. The term c/s measures the supersaturation coefficient and is an inverse measure of the particle size (τ). It is quite easy to show that conditions for precipitation of micro-particles are similar to those which prevail when the finer particles in a colloidal state come together and begin to precipitate, if one allows for the viscosity of the solution. In other words, Von Weimarn's equation leads to the same conclusion as in equation (1) until colloidal dimensions are approached.

The viscosity factor in equation (1) is included in the constant K

$$K = \frac{2M\sigma}{RTd} = \frac{2V_1\sigma}{PV} \quad \dots (3)$$

where P is the osmotic pressure, V , the volume of the solution and V_1 , the volume of the solute particles.

In the region of colloidal solutions (Einstein, *Ann. Physik*, 1906, **19**, 289)

$$\frac{V}{V_1} = \frac{\eta_1 - \eta_0}{K_1 \eta_0}$$

where η_0 is the viscosity of the dispersion medium and η_1 is that of the disperse system ; K_1 is a constant.

Substituting in (1)

$$\frac{\tau(S - S_n)}{S_n} \left(\frac{\eta_0}{\eta_1 - \eta_0} \right) = \frac{K_2 \sigma}{P}$$

where K_2 is constant.

This equation is a more complete representation of the factors involved than that given by equation (2) and has dimensions.

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Received August 8, 1947.